

The Advantages of Online Learning: Critical Analysis

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Abstract. There are a lot of names for online learning such as e-learning, distance learning, online education and all of them have the same definition which is a form of education and learning that involve students to not always be fully attending schools. Seeing as the amount of universities has offered online learning courses increases, the courses have begun to grow and become diverse and also the rate of students applying to these courses are growing, this factor has raised a few doubts about whether any of the education provided will be as effective as it could be (Manijeh Sadeghi, 2019). People view online learning as a great thing to happen because they can learn at a flexible time and place. This paper will discuss the advantages of online learning for students and educators for a better learning experience.

Keywords: online learning, advantages, universities, study, internet, education

Introduction

There are a lot of names for online learning such as e-learning, distance learning, online education and all of them have the same definition which is a form of education and learning that involve students to not always be fully attending schools. To put it in another way, with online learning students can learn to study in their preferred online courses without having to visit a college building or university campus (Manijeh Sadeghi, 2019). Online learning has also been made possible by the existing of internet, and numbers of researchers and educator are intrigued with the idea of online learning that they think would enhance and develop the students learning end result primarily in higher education (Farinella, Hobbs, & Weeks, 2000; Kim & Bonk, 2006; Pape, 2010). Not only at colleges but in elementary and secondary schools too, online learning seems to be an irreplaceable portion of the educational procedure. It can now be described as a learning medium that uses

communication tools, information and also digital media (Blanka Klimova & Petra Maresova, 2016). This learning style originally began in the United States around the 1800's when at that time the students and educators at the University of Chicago attempted to connect via correspondence programs (Mclsaac & Gunawardena, 1996). Ever since, online courses as well as the entire degree programs online were offered to universities and colleges not only in the United States but around the world too (Wallace, 2003). Moreover, online courses usually make use of a variety of new technologies that can make it simpler to communicate with other people and quite systematic more than anything where students can successfully learn to utilize e-mails, interactive videos and discussion boards to finish their work task (Velasenko & Bozhok, 2014).

Modern technologies nowadays have become an inseparable part of today's young generation lives. The involvement of technology these days in education has created an online environment that introduces new approaches in providing knowledge and information to students (Titan, Ferdianto, GG Faniru Pakuning Desak & Lena, 2017). Seeing as the amount of universities has offered online learning courses increases, the courses have begun to grow and become diverse and also the rate of students applying to these courses are growing, this factor has raised a few doubts about whether any of the education provided will be as effective as it could be (Manijeh Sadeghi, 2019). This paper will discuss the advantages of online learning for students and educators for a better learning experience.

Advantages of Online Learning

Flexibility

The large number of online learning in this era requires the use of the internet according to Ryan (1997) because whether it is in their own homes or facilities such as the library, the internet can now be access by many students easily. With the rise of technology, research has become far more accessible for distance learning students over the last 20 years. It was mentioned by Zigerell (1984) that modern technologies have made it easier to connect educational institutions to workplaces and homes. However, as stated by Traxler (2018), in formal online learning, there is huge potential for better access to higher education and also the rise of student population diversity as digital technologies offers great chances for everyone to study anywhere at any time. People view online learning as a great thing to happen because they can learn at a flexible time and place. Moreover, people can participate in the courses and begin to learn at any part of the world they live in (Manijeh Sadeghi, 2019). Various ways of online learning give learners opportunity to set their own schedule according to their preference without having to follow a regular schedule. Other flexibility is that online learning gives them the freedom to select their own course programme (Brown, 2017). There are many universities and other institutions globally that provide this kind of opportunity for students to learn online. Furthermore, Manijeh Sadeghi (2019) said that online learning encourages students to not only study

anywhere they want but also, they can arrange their studies around their family and working life. In addition, these methods of teaching allow educators to teach at their own home and timetable according to their own hours of teaching. A flexible working timetable is certainly reachable due to the wide internet accessibility and educational sources within easy reach (Manijeh Sadeghi, 2019).

Time and Cost Saving

Bijeesh (2017) mentions that for any specific program given, the online educational degree fee can be far more reasonable than the fee for a normal on-campus degree class. Other than that, Brown (2017), also states that it is more affordable to study the courses offered at an online learning centres rather than the course provided at a traditional education centre. For students that are searching for a cost-effective alternative option can choose online learning programs as they don't have to remain at the same spot to take part in the studies at the academic universities of their preference. Students can obtain full access to technologies such as a computer and also internet connection so they can study. The cumulative national student loan debt is more than one trillion dollars as of 2014 (Finaid.org, 2014). Numerous scholars and educators have agreed that online learning is a successful method to tackle the rising cost of postsecondary education. (Bowen, 2013; Bartley & Golek, 2004; Jung & Rha, 2000; Koller & Ng, 2014; Tucker, 2007).

Bijeesh (2017) argued that attending to and from college can waste time when students need to wait for their form of transportation such as bus or train. Also, Nagrale (2013) says that you do not have to travel in crowded buses or trains when choosing online education. However, with online learning, students can now study in their rooms and have all the materials they need on their desk and computer. As an option, this is great for students who may not have sufficient time on their hands can choose online learning to pursue simply from home. The entire university can be present in the student's bedroom without having to go outside of their house. Travelling to universities is a tiring part of studying as it wastes a lot of time and money as well as energy (Manijeh Sadeghi, 2019).

Broad Internet Access

Students can get all the knowledge and course materials anywhere in the universe even if the course offered by an international school yet the students might easily get the access to other materials as well (Nagrale, 2013). Moreover, students often utilize their study materials and get information from online learning platforms that are meant for active learning. They also can interact with other people with the same course as them globally via the virtual learning environment (Manijeh Sadeghi, 2019). Speaking of a broad internet access, teachers on the other hand can manage their virtual teaching from their own technologies anywhere that they want in the world which at the same time allows them to have the freedom to travel or fly around the world. They just need to be prepared and have a great connection to access the

internet and virtually reach out to their students from places to places (Manijeh Sadeghi, 2019). Lastly, it is possible for online learning to give out a world class education to anybody, whenever and wherever they are as long they have a great internet connection. Khan Academy, Udacity, edX, and Coursera are one of the most outstanding websites and companies that are built for scholars and entrepreneurs that have high expectations for online learning, especially for huge open online courses (Bowen, 2013; Fisher, 2012; Koller & Ng, 2012; Lewin, 2012; Selingo, 2013).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the idea of online learning is very suitable in these technological eras which is why students need to know about the existence of it so they can choose from these options to help them when they have difficulties in doing on campus classes. Finch and Jacobs (2012) acknowledged these advantages in addressing online learning proper practices that can save travel time and costs, increase access opportunities and collaborating with professional practitioners that is on a massive scale, assists students with flexibility to access courses at their comfort, and encouraging changes to subjects and material needs. It is recommended to learn and hold onto reliable sources on the Internet as the world wide web provides so much useful information for students to do their research or studies. Moreover, it saves money and time as students can learn without having to pay for too much for education as well as it saves their time by not having to go out and to have transportation problems such as waiting for busses or local trains to attend their physical classes. Other than that, with online learning, students and also educators can have the flexibility to learn and teach wherever they are as long as they have the internet connection to do so.

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